

EXPRESSIONS INDICATING PLURALITY AND UNITY IN KAZAN TATAR TURKISH

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ABSTRACT: Language is one of the most important indicators reflecting the way humans think, and the concept of plurality holds a fundamental position among these indicators. The concept of plurality is one of the special categories established in languages through different structures such as suffixes, words, and word groups. As in Turkish languages in general, plurality in Tatar Turkish expresses not only numerical excess but also an indefinite, abstract plurality. In this respect, the category of plurality encompasses not only quantitative excess but also conceptual plurality. Although literature reviews generally reveal intensive studies on plural suffixes, research on words indicating plurality and unity appears to be limited. This study aims to identify structures indicating plurality and unity in Tatar Turkish, which belongs to the Northwestern/Kipchak group of Turkic dialects, and to evaluate the semantic functions of these structures.

Keywords: Tatar Turkish, plurality, unity, Kipchak group

INTRODUCTION

Language is the most fundamental means of communication that shapes how humans perceive the world and interpret social reality. The concept of plurality is a special category established in languages through different structures such as suffixes, words, and word groups. In Turkic languages, plurality carries a morphological function that expresses more than one entity or phenomenon, while the concept of unity encompasses the meanings of togetherness, partnership, and reciprocity. Tatar Turkish, while belonging to the Kipchak group of Turkic dialects, stands out as an important written language that continues the fundamental characteristics of historical Turkish in a contemporary form. In this dialect, plurality is mostly expressed with the suffix -lar/-lär, but in some cases it is also expressed through the semantic expansion of words.

Scientific studies have focused more on plural suffixes. Important local and foreign linguists such as Munkasci, Budenz, Räsänen, Fucs, Bang, Poppe; Serebrennikov, Gabain, Gadjeva, Grönbech, Alkaya, and Gülsevin have conducted studies on the plural suffix +lAr (Alkaya, 2010: 31-33). Poppe (2008: 93-110) discusses the diversity of plural suffixes in Altaic languages; Janhunen (2018: 485-895) mentions the existence of the *-s plural suffix; and Ata (2009: 89-99) points to a primary +lA plural suffix. Hazar (2003: 131-141) mentions the plural suffix +(I)z; Başdaş (2007: 291-296), Ulutaş (2007: 1-6), and Dinler (2020: 179-196) mention that the -ş- reciprocal suffix takes on the task of indicating plurality of persons. Yalçın (2021: 1-12) points to the +gil suffix; Alkaya and Yalçın (2022) point to the *l plural suffix. İlhan (2009 and 2017); Başdaş (2011); Alyılmaz (2017) comprehensively address the plural suffixes found in the Turkish language.

In the literature review, while intensive studies on plural suffixes are generally found, studies on Turkish words indicating plurality and unity are seen to be negligible. In our study, the Tatar Turkish Dictionary was used as a basis, and expressions indicating plurality and unity in this dictionary were attempted to be identified.

KAZAN-TATAR TURKISH DICTIONARY

artık	KNTTS:28	"Çok (many)"
aruv	KNTTS:28	"Oldukça (quite)"
azmı	KNTTS:32	"Bir Çok (many), pek Çok (many)"
barça	KNTTS:34	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely), tamamı (complete), tamamen (complete)"
barı	KNTTS:34	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely), bütün, tamamı (complete)"
barı da	KNTTS:34	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
barlık	KNTTS:35	"Bütün, Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
başlıca	KNTTS:36	"çoğu (most) zaman (most of the time)"
bay	KNTTS:37	"Çok (many), fazla (too much)"
baytağ	KNTTS:37	"Çok (many)ça, pek Çok (many)"
bër	KNTTS:40	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
bër avızdan	KNTTS:40	"Hep birlikte (collectively)"
berdem	KNTTS:40	"Hep beraber (collectively)"
bërek	KNTTS:40	"toplanmak (to gather)"
bërge bërge	KNTTS:40	"topluca (all together)"
bëryulı	KNTTS:41	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
bëtmes	KNTTS:41	"Çok (many)"
bigayet	KNTTS:42	"Sınırsız, pek Çok (many)"
bigük	KNTTS:42	"Pek Çok (many), pek fazla (too much)"
biter	KNTTS:43	"Çok (many) fazla (too much)"
bol (abundant)	KNTTS:44	"fazla (too much)"
boz	KNTTS:46	"dolu(full)"
böten	KNTTS:47	"tam (complete), Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
cemeğatçëlëk	KNTTS:52	"toplum (society)"
cemğı	KNTTS:52	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely), tamamı (complete) bütünü"
cıynav	KNTTS:54	"Hep beraber, topluca (all together) (collectively)"
citerlëk	KNTTS:58	"bol (abundant)"
cömle	KNTTS:58	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely, bütün, topluluk"
cöp	KNTTS:58	"çift (double)"
çağıştırğısız	KNTTS:60	"Epeyce, Çok (many)"
çoq	KNTTS:60	"tam (complete)"
çaqlı	KNTTS:60	"tamamen (complete), Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
çamasız	KNTTS:61	"Sınırsız miktarda Çok (many)"
çëm	KNTTS:64	"Pek fazla (too much), Çok (many)"
çiksëz	KNTTS:67	"Pek Çok (many)"
derya	KNTTS:72	"bol (abundant), Çok (many)"
diñgëz	KNTTS:74	"bol (abundant)luk"
döm	KNTTS:74	"tam (complete)amen"
fırqa	KNTTS:91	"bölük (team), takım"
ğalem	KNTTS:98	"Topluluk, grup, fazla (too much)"
hemme	KNTTS:101	"Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
her	KNTTS:101	"Hepsi, tamamı (complete), (all / entire / completely), bütünü"

hisapsız	KNTTS:109	"Çok (many)"
ifrat	KNTTS:116	"Çok (many),aşırı,fazla (too much)"
ille	KNTTS:118	"Pek Çok (many), fazla (too much)sıyla"
kette	KNTTS:130	"Büyük,Çok (many),fazla (too much)"
kiñ	KNTTS:134	"Çok (many),dolu(full)"
kiñlek	KNTTS:135	"dolu(full)luk, tam (complete)lık"
köşel	KNTTS:142	"Bir Çok (many), bir sürü"
kübev	KNTTS:144	"Çok (many)"
küme (cluster)	KNTTS:146	"küme (cluster)"
küp	KNTTS:147	"Çok (many),fazla (too much),sayısı veya miktarı yüksek"
küberek	KNTTS:147	"Daha Çok (many)"
kübësë	KNTTS:147	"çoğu (most)"
küplep	KNTTS:147	"Çok miktarda (many),Çok (many) Çok (many)"
küp son	KNTTS:147	"Çok sayıda(many) "
küpçëlëk	KNTTS:147	"çoğunluk (most) (majority)"
küplep	KNTTS:147	"Çokluk(many)"
küpmëdër	KNTTS:147	"Çok (many),pek Çok (many)"
küpsën	KNTTS:147	"Bir şeyin tahminen Çok (many) olduğunu söylemek"
kalın	KNTTS:155	"dolu(full)"
koçak	KNTTS:171	"Pek Çok (many)"
koçakçıç	KNTTS:175	"fazla (too much),artık"
mëñlep	KNTTS:192	"Çok (many)"
mir	KNTTS:195	"insan topluluğu (group of people)"
mul	KNTTS:197	"bol (abundant), pek Çok (many)"
nıbarı	KNTTS:202	"Hepsi, (all / entire / completely), tamamı (complete), toplam"
nihayet	KNTTS:202	"Pek fazla (too much)"
nikader	KNTTS:203	"Pek Çok (many)"
öçev	KNTTS:211	"üçü birlikte (all three)"
ör	KNTTS:212	"Pek Çok (many)"
rota	KNTTS:224	"bölük (team)"
tap	KNTTS:264	"tam (complete)"
tögel	KNTTS:288	"tam (complete)"
tömen(I)	KNTTS:289	"Çok (many),fazla (too much)"
tuk	KNTTS:294	"dolu(full)"
tulayım	KNTTS:295	"Bütünüyle,Hepsi (all / entire / completely)"
tulı	KNTTS:295	"dolu(full),tam (complete)"
uq	KNTTS:302	"Pek,Çok (many)"
uñğa	KNTTS:304	"Pek Çok (many)"
zapas	KNTTS:356	"fazlalık (too much)"
zëre	KNTTS:357	"Çok (many),fazla (too much)"
zur	KNTTS:358	"fazla (too much),Çok (many)"

CONCLUSION

In our study, which focuses on words indicating plurality and unity in Kazan Tatar Turkish, 83 entries indicating plurality and unity were identified by scanning the Kazan Tatar Dictionary prepared by Mustafa Öner and published by the Turkish Language Association in 2015.

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